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The relations between extended stratified domination number and maximum degree and order of a connected graph

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ABSTRACT

A graph G is 2-stratified if its vertex set partitioned into two colour classes. We colour the vertices in one colour class red and the other class blue. Let F be 2-stratified graph rooted at one fixed blue vertex v specified. The F -domination number of a graph G is the minimum number of red vertices of G in a red-blue colouring of the vertices of G such that every blue vertex v of G belongs to a copy of F rooted at v . Let $F = \{F_1, \dots, F_k\}$, where F_i , $1 \leq i \leq k$, is a 2-stratified graph rooted at some blue vertex v . The F^* -domination number of G (extended stratified domination) is defined as the minimum number red vertices of G in a red-blue colouring of the vertices of G such that every blue vertex v of G belongs to a copy of F_i rooted at v for at least one value of i . In this short letter we investigate the relation between F^* -domination number (extended stratified domination number) and maximum degree and order of a connected graph when the extension F^* is acquired the stratified F_1 and F_5 graphs which are shown in Fig.1.

Keywords: Stratified domination, Extended stratified domination, Maximum degree, Order

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Introduction and Basics

Chartrand et al. [1] started the study combining stratification and domination in graphs. A graph G is 2-stratified if its vertex set partitioned into two colour classes. We colour the vertices in one colour class red and the other class blue. Let F be 2-stratified graph rooted at one fixed blue vertex v specified. The F -domination number (stratified domination) of a graph G is the minimum number of red vertices of G in a red-blue colouring of the vertices of G such that every blue vertex v of G belongs to a copy of F rooted at v .

The main research is focused on stratified domination number comes from the five stratified graphs which are in showed Fig.1.

Figure 1The five basic stratified graphs

Below theorem states that the strong relations between in stratified domination number and other type domination numbers.

Theorem 2 ([1]). Let G be a connected graph of order at least 3.

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(a) If $F = F_1$, then $\gamma_{F(G)} = \gamma_t(G)$.

(b) If $F = F_2$, then $\gamma_{F(G)} = \gamma(G)$.

(c) If $F = F_4$, then $\gamma_{F(G)} = \gamma_r(G)$.

(d) If $F = F_5$, then $\gamma_{F(G)} = \gamma_2(G)$.

Notice that where $\gamma_t(G)$ stands for total domination number, $\gamma(G)$ stands for ordinary domination number, $\gamma_r(G)$ means restrained domination number and $\gamma_2(G)$ means 2-step domination number.

For further and detailed studies stratified domination see the following references [2-17].

In [18], F^* -domination defined as an extended version of stratified domination:

Let $F = \{F_1, \dots, F_k\}$, where F_i , $1 \leq i \leq k$, is a 2- stratified graph rooted at some blue vertex v . The F^* -domination number of G is defined as the minimum number red vertices of G in a red-blue colouring of the vertices of G such that every blue vertex v of G belongs to a copy of F_i rooted at v for at least one value of i .

And now we begin to investigate the relation between F^* -domination number (extended stratified domination number) and maximum degree and order of a connected graph when the extension F is acquired the stratified F_1 and F_5 graphs which are shown Fig.1.

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Extended stratified domination number and maximum degree with order a graph

In this section we give two theorems which states the relation between extended stratified domination number and maximum degree with order of a connected graph G . Here, we choose $F = \{F_1, F_5\}$.

Theorem 1. Let G be a connected graph with order is greater than two ($n \geq 3$) and $F = \{F_1, F_5\}$. Then $\gamma_{F^*(G)} \leq n - \Delta + 1$ where Δ is the maximum degree of the graph G .

Proof. We proceed by induction on Δ . If $\Delta = 2$ then G must be a path or a cycle that the inequality holds for. Let suppose that the inequality holds for $\Delta = k \leq n - 2$. And now we show that the inequality holds for $\Delta = k + 1$. Let G be a connected graph $\Delta = k$. We can get the connected graph H with $\Delta = k + 1$ from G . For this, we add a new vertex w to the graph G . Here notice that this novel vertex w is adjacent to the maximum degree of G namely v and at most $\Delta - 1$ vertices of G . Thus, H be a novel graph with $\Delta = k + 1$. This situation is showed in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 *H* acquired from *G*

Since the aim of F-colouring is to use the fewest number of red vertices, the vertex where the maximum degree is obtained must be coloured red. Therefore, the colour of the vertex v must be red. It is also obvious that there will be red vertices among the neighbours of v . Therefore, it is obvious that the colour of the vertex w in graph H will be blue. Thus, the number of red vertices in graphs H and G will be equal.

Instead of the inequality $\gamma_{F^*(G)} \leq n - \Delta + 1$ that we wrote for the graph G , the inequality $\gamma_{F^*(H)} \leq n - \Delta + 1$ can be written. Here, considering that $\Delta =$

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$k + 1$ for H , we have $\gamma_{F^*(G)} \leq n - \Delta + 1 = (n + 1) - (k + 1) + 1 = (n + 1) - \Delta + 1$. Thus, the proof ends.

Proposition 2. Let P_n be a path and $F = \{F_1, F_5\}$. Then,

a-) $\gamma_{F^*(P_n)} = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1 \quad (n \equiv 1, 2, 3 \pmod{4})$

b-) $\gamma_{F^*(P_n)} = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1 \quad (n \equiv 0 \pmod{4})$

Proof. (a) Consider an n -path graph P_n with vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n lined up sequentially. If n is odd, colouring the vertices $v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-2}, v_n$ red gives an F^* -colouring of P_n . If $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, colouring the vertices $v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}, v_n$ red gives an F^* -colouring of P_n . Therefore,

$$\gamma_{F^*(P_n)} \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1.$$

Now, let's show that for the 2-partitioned 3-path graphs in Figure 1, $\gamma_{F^*(P_n)} \geq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$. Assume that $\gamma_{F^*(P_n)} = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. In this case, if n is odd, the number of blue vertices exceeds the number of red vertices by 1, which is a contradiction. If $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, the number of red and blue vertices would be equal. In this case, let $0 \leq k$ and k be an integer such that $n = 4k + 2$. Then the vertices $v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{4k+1}$ will be red and the vertices $v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{4k+2}$ will be blue. However, for any F^* -colouring with vertex v_{4k+2} taken as the root, the

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vertices v_{4k+1} and v_{4k} must also be red. This is a contradiction. Therefore,

$$\gamma_{F^*(P_n)} \geq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1.$$

(b) Let $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. Colouring the vertices $v_2, v_3, v_6, v_7, \dots, v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}$ of red gives a F^* -colouring of P_n . Therefore, $\gamma_{F^*(P_n)} \geq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. Suppose that $\gamma_{F^*(P_n)} = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1$. In this case, any F^* -colouring of P_n contains two adjacent blue vertices, and there is no F_1 and F_5 graph considering these blue vertices as roots. Thus, the proof is complete.

Proposition 3. Let C_n be a cycle and $F = \{F_1, F_5\}$. Then,

a-) $\gamma_{F^*(C_n)} = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ (*n is odd*)

b-) $\gamma_{F^*(C_n)} = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ (*n is even*)

Proof. (a) Let n be odd integer, and consider an n -cycle graph with vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n . Colouring the vertices $v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}, v_{n-2}$ of the graph red gives an F^* -colouring of C_n . Therefore, $\gamma_{F^*(C_n)} \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$. Suppose that $\gamma_{F^*(C_n)} = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. In this case, the number of blue vertices would be greater than the number of red vertices, which is a contradiction. Therefore, $\gamma_{F^*(C_n)} \geq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$.

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(b) For n is even, an n -cycle graph with vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n , the red colouring of vertices v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1} of the n -cycle gives an F^* -colouring of the n -cycle. Therefore, $\gamma_{F^*(C_n)} \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. Now we will show that $\gamma_{F^*(C_n)} \geq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. Suppose that $\gamma_{F^*(C_n)} = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1$. In this case, any F^* -colouring of C_n would contain at least three adjacent blue vertices, for which there is no F_1 and F_5 graph taking these blue vertices as roots. Therefore, $\gamma_{F^*(C_n)} \geq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$.

Theorem 4. Let G be a connected graph with order is greater than two ($n \geq 3$) and $F = \{F_1, F_5\}$. Then $\gamma_{F^*(G)} \leq 2n/3$.

Proof. If G is any complete graph, complete bipartite graph, path graph, or cycle graph, it is easily seen that the inequality holds in the light of Proposition 2 and Proposition 3. Considering together the expression $\gamma_{F^*(G)} \leq n - \Delta + 1$ proven in Theorem 1, let us assume that $\gamma_{F^*(G)} > 2n/3$. From this, we can write $\frac{2n}{3} < \gamma_{F^*(G)} \leq n - \Delta + 1$. And again, from these inequalities, it follows that $\frac{2n}{3} < n - \Delta + 1$. Thus, the inequality $\Delta < n/3 + 1$ is obtained. For $n=3$, we get $\Delta=1$, and the only graph satisfying this condition is the K_2 graph of order $n=2$, which is a contradiction regarding the graph H obtained from graph G in Figure 2. For $n=6$, we get $\Delta=2$, in which case G is either a path graph or a cycle graph. If G is a path graph, in the light of

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Proposition 2, we obtain $\gamma_{F^*(G)} = 4 > \frac{2n}{3} = 2 * \frac{6}{3} = 4$ which is also a contradiction. If G is a cycle graph, in the light of Proposition 3, we obtain the inequality $\gamma_{F^*(G)} = 3 > \frac{2n}{3} = 2 * \frac{6}{3} = 4$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, our assumption is false. From this, we obtain $\gamma_{F^*(G)} \leq 2n/3$. Thus, the proof is complete.

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